

Investigation of Tandem Propellers with Varying Design Configurations

Kiran George Varghese^{1*}, Anirban Bhattacharyya¹

¹ Dept. of Ocean Engineering and Naval Architecture, IIT Kharagpur, West Bengal, INDIA

Abstract

Marine tandem propellers are suitable for inland vessels operating in restricted water depths. A tandem propeller unit typically consists of two corotating propellers; the propeller which faces the inflow first is termed the forward propeller, and the subsequent one is termed the aft propeller. The design of the aft propeller has to be carefully chosen as it is located in the slipstream of the forward propeller. In the present study, the forward and aft propellers in tandem are designed using an in-house vortex lattice lifting-line method (VLLM) incorporating lifting surface corrections. The VLLM approaches are used to design a tandem propeller subjected to various design configurations such as propeller diameter, number of blades, and inflow velocity distribution.

The pitch distribution over the propeller blades and the pitch difference between the forward and aft propellers are critical factors for optimal performance. The influence of pitch distribution for a given thrust input on the design of tandem propellers is investigated. The relative performance of the design variants is dependent on the propeller advance coefficient. Numerical computations using CFD are performed to understand the underlying flow characteristics for different configurations. Model open water tests for a specific design of tandem propellers are performed for validation.

Tandem propellers can be considered a practical solution for vessels which require high thrust loading, where the tandem propellers can distribute the thrust between the forward and aft propellers operating from a single propeller shaft and engine, and also for those vessels which operate in shallow water depth..

Keywords: *Tandem propellers, Thrust, Efficiency, Vortex lattice lifting-line method (VLLM), CFD, Open water experiments.*

1 Introduction

A tandem propeller configuration consists of a series of co-rotating propellers, typically two in number and mounted coaxially. One of the initial applications of tandem propellers in a vessel can be traced from the 19th century for a vessel named ‘Turbinia’ [1], [2]. From the published literature, it can be observed that when compared to a conventional single propeller unit, tandem propellers have a larger optimal efficiency when the available propeller diameter is small [3]. From the outcome of some experimental trials where a tandem propeller unit was compared with a conventional propeller for various vessels such as tugs, coasters and high-power ice-breaking LNG carriers, the tandem propellers performed better [4]. It has also been reported [5] The usage of tandem propellers can help in reducing the periodic loads acting on the propeller unit at certain frequencies. Hence, the tandem propellers can be considered a suitable propulsion unit, especially for inland waters where the propeller diameter is often limited due to constraints in water depth.

The available literature related to numerical works on tandem propellers is scarce. Parametric studies on tandem propellers can be observed from previous literature, where the influence of geometrical particulars such as axial spacing, angular spacing and diameter ratio on the tandem propellers' performance was documented [4], [6], [7], [8], [9]. Numerical studies focused on cavitation indicate that a forward tandem propeller is more crucial to cavitation [10]. In one of the recent studies, the hydrodynamic performance of the B-series propeller in tandem configuration was studied along with some parametric investigations. It was observed that the aft tandem propeller works in an inferior manner when conventional standard pitch distributions are considered [11]. However, when the tandem propellers are designed considering the wake induced into the individual propellers, the total performance of the tandem propellers could be improved [12]. In the present study, the tandem propellers

considered are designed using the vortex lattice lifting-line method (VLLM) developed in-house, incorporating lifting-surface corrections.

Table 1. Nomenclature

Z	Number of blades
D	Propeller diameter
P/D	Pitch to diameter ratio
A_E/A_0	Expanded blade area ratio
L/D	Axial spacing ratio
θ	Angular spacing
T	Propeller thrust
Q	Propeller torque
ρ	Fluid density
n	Revolution per second
V_A	Advance speed
K_T	Thrust coefficient
K_Q	Torque coefficient
η_o	Propeller open water efficiency
J	Advance ratio
C_P	Pressure coefficient
x/c	Ratio of axial length to blade chord length

2 Propeller Geometry

The representation of a tandem propeller unit when attached to a vessel is shown in Fig. 1. The propeller which faces the inflow first is termed the forward propeller, and the subsequent propeller is termed the aft propeller. The forward and aft propellers are represented by 'Fwd.' and 'Aft' respectively.

Figure 1. Representation of tandem propellers with the orientation when attached to a ship: (a) Front view, (b) Side view

The various geometrical particulars of the tandem propellers considered for this manuscript are represented in Table 2. The pitch of the aft propeller is larger than the pitch of the forward tandem propeller. A pitch difference of 0.2 is maintained, which is similar to a previous study. [6]. The axial spacing (L) of the tandem propellers can

be visualised in Fig.1 (b). In Fig. 1 (a) and Fig. 1 (b), the angular spacing (θ) is maintained at zero degrees for representation purposes.

Table 2. Propeller particulars

Parameter	Dimension
Z	4
D_{Fwd}	0.10m, 0.105m, 0.111m
D_{Aft}	0.10m, 0.105m, 0.111m
$(P/D)_{Fwd.}$	1.08
$(P/D)_{Aft}$	1.28
$(A_E/A_0)_{Fwd.}$	0.55
$(A_E/A_0)_{Aft.}$	0.55
L/D	0.25
θ	38.30 degrees, 83.30 degrees

3 Methodology

The performance of a marine propeller is usually expressed in terms of the open water coefficients [1], [2]. These coefficients are expressed as mentioned below.

$$K_{T\ Total} = \frac{T_{Fwd} + T_{Aft}}{\rho n^2 D^4} \quad (1)$$

$$K_{Q\ Total} = \frac{Q_{Fwd} + Q_{Aft}}{\rho n^2 D^5} \quad (2)$$

$$\eta_{o\ Total} = \frac{J}{2\pi} * \frac{K_{T\ Total}}{K_{Q\ Total}} \quad (3)$$

$$J = \frac{V_A}{n D} \quad (4)$$

In the above equations, $K_{T\ Total}$, $K_{Q\ Total}$, $\eta_{o\ Total}$, and J represent the tandem propellers' thrust coefficient, torque coefficient, open water efficiency and advance ratio, respectively.

3.1 Vortex Lattice Lifting-Line Method with Lifting Surface Corrections

The principle behind the VLLM procedure is to determine the optimum radial circulation distribution for a given marine propeller unit and thereby obtain the radial pitch distributions for the propeller blades by considering the lifting surface corrections. The procedure for designing tandem propellers based on VLLM and lifting surface corrections is explained in detail in the previous studies. [12], [13]. The tandem propellers considered in the present study are designed using an in-house vortex lattice lifting-line method (VLLM) incorporating lifting surface corrections.

3.2 Model Tests

The open-water testing of the marine tandem propellers was performed at the towing tank facility at the Indian Institute of Technology Kharagpur. As mentioned in section 3.1, the tandem propellers are designed using the VLLM approach and lifting surface corrections. The diameter of the tandem propellers manufactured was 0.1 m. The forward and aft propellers were positioned at an angular spacing of 38.30 degrees, and the ratio of axial length to propeller diameter (L/D) was kept at 0.25. The detailed particulars of the tandem propellers are provided in

Table 2. The model tandem propellers used for the experiments are represented in Fig. 2(a). The open-water experiments were performed at various values of advance coefficients (J), maintaining a constant rotational speed of 600 rpm at varying carriage speeds. The experimental setup is represented in Fig. 2(b). Based on the capacity of the experimental facility, the Reynolds number considered is in the range of 5.65×10^4 to 6.75×10^4 .

Figure 2: Model testing: (a)The fabricated tandem propellers for testing, the propeller orientation is for open water testing purposes; (b) Open water testing at the Indian Institute of Technology Kharagpur

3.3 CFD Investigations

The numerical analysis of the tandem propeller is performed using the RANS solver of Star CCM+, incorporating the moving reference frame (MRF) technique. A transition model incorporating the $k-\omega$ -SST turbulence model with the γ - Re_{θ} transition model was considered in the study. The details of the transition modelling for marine propellers are based on a previous study [14]. The computational domain consists of two regions represented by cylinders: the inner cylinder, named the rotating region, representing the fluid region around the tandem propellers, whereas the outer cylinder represents the static fluid domain. An interface separates the rotating and the static regions. The dimensions of the domain are as specified in Fig.3 (a). A trimmed celled mesh type was considered for the static domain, whereas a polyhedral mesh type was adopted in the rotating region, with a refined mesh in the propeller blades. The mesh pattern can be observed in Fig. 3 (b)

Figure 3. (a)Representation of the domain and boundary for the propeller open water CFD simulation. (b) The mesh representation of the tandem propellers, in which the forward and aft propellers are angularly spaced

A grid convergence study is performed, considering three mesh sizes named medium, fine and very fine, and the base size is varied at an interval of $\sqrt{2}$. The $10K_Q$ Total value at three different mesh sizes at two different advance coefficients ($J = 0.4$ and $J = 0.85$) is represented in Fig.4. The error percentage between the fine and very fine mesh sizes is less than 1%. Therefore, the fine mesh size was considered for performing the numerical study.

Figure 4. Grid-independent study with three mesh sizes

4 Results and Discussion

To understand the performance of the tandem propeller unit under various design requirements and geometrical parameters, the following investigations are carried out.

4.1. Validation

Open water experiments on tandem propellers are performed (As mentioned in section 3.2). The tandem propellers are designed based on the VLLM approach, incorporating lifting surface corrections to produce thrust equivalent to a thrust coefficient ($K_{T \text{ Total}}$) of 0.31 operating at an advance ratio (J) of 0.84. This corresponds to the design point in the open water characteristic plot and is represented by the green-coloured marker. Compared to the total thrust obtained from the open water tests (represented as Exp) in Fig. 5, it can be observed that the tandem propellers are capable of generating the thrust for which it was designed with an acceptable level of accuracy. Additionally, the same experimental data are used to validate the CFD simulations. The CFD and experimental results are also comparable, as represented in Fig. 5. Hence, the particular numerical setup was considered for the upcoming CFD simulations.

Figure 5. Validation of the VLLM design point and CFD simulations with the experimental results

4.2. VLLM Design Output Variation

The inputs required for designing a tandem propeller are: total propeller thrust, thrust division between the forward and aft tandem propellers, operating inflow velocity and rpm, as well as other geometric parameters. The output from the VLLM procedure, i.e., the propeller geometry (radial P/D distribution), will vary based on the inputs the user provides. To understand the trend of the VLLM output, the total propeller thrust is varied.

Figure 6. Plot from the VLLM approach for different values of the total thrust coefficient ($K_{T \text{ Total}}$) vs (a) Mean P/D difference between the aft and forward tandem propellers, (b) Open water efficiency of the tandem propeller unit ($\eta_{O \text{ Total}}$)

All other input parameters, such as propeller diameter, revolution rate and inflow velocity, are kept constant. The variation of the mean pitch difference between the aft and forward tandem propellers with $K_{T \text{ Total}}$ and the variation of $\eta_{O \text{ Total}}$ with $K_{T \text{ Total}}$ are represented in Fig. 6(a) and Fig.6 (b) respectively.

For tandem propellers, as the aft propeller is working in the disturbed wake field of the forward propeller, the pitch distribution required by the aft propeller is larger; this observation is documented in one of our previous studies [13]. It should be noted that the term mean pitch difference indicates the difference in pitch between the aft and forward tandem propellers. From the plots represented in Fig. 6, it can be inferred that the mean pitch difference increases with the propeller loading. However, the open water efficiency initially increases, reaches a peak, and gradually dips down. A similar trend of the mean pitch difference with the propeller loading was mentioned in our previous study [6]. The total thrust loading should be adopted based on the operational requirements of the vessel/ship for which the propeller is designed.

4.3. Parametric Study

A parametric investigation is performed to understand the tandem propeller performance when subjected to geometrical parameters such as the diameter ratio and the angular spacing. The blade area ratio, axial spacing ratio and the mean pitch of the forward and aft propeller are maintained constant in this parametric study for comparison purposes.

4.3.1 Diameter Ratio

The diameter ratios ($D_{\text{Fwd}} / D_{\text{Aft}}$) are varied from 0.90, 0.95, 1.0, 1.05 and 1.10. In addition to the parameters mentioned above, the angular spacing is also maintained at a constant of 38.30 degrees; the strategy for considering this particular angular spacing is mentioned in the upcoming section. The values of the forward and aft propeller diameters considered are indicated in Table 3.

Table 3. The diameters of the forward and aft tandem propellers are varied in the study and are represented. Note: The minimum propeller diameter is maintained at 0.1m

$D_{\text{Fwd}}/D_{\text{Aft}}$	0.90	0.95	1.00	1.05	1.10
D_{Fwd}	0.100	0.100	0.100	0.105	0.111
D_{Aft}	0.111	0.105	0.100	0.100	0.100

When; ($D_{\text{Fwd}} / D_{\text{Aft}} = 1$), it indicates that both forward and aft propellers have the same diameter. In the first two cases, the aft propeller diameter is kept larger ($D_{\text{Aft}} > D_{\text{Fwd}}$), whereas the forward propeller is kept larger in the last two cases ($D_{\text{Fwd}} > D_{\text{Aft}}$). In all the combinations considered the minimum propeller diameter is maintained at 0.1 m. Fig. 7 represents the different combinations of diameter ratios considered.

Figure 7. Representation of the different diameter ratios considered. The propeller orientation represented is such that it is in the behind-hull condition, similar to Fig.1

The open water curves are used to predict the performance at different propeller configurations. It can be observed that the tandem propeller unit with a larger aft propeller diameter produces more thrust, which can be observed by the thrust coefficient represented in Fig.8 (a). The tandem propeller unit with a diameter ratio of 0.90 produces the highest $K_{T \text{ Total}}$ for the entire range of advance coefficients considered, followed by the diameter ratios 0.95, 1,1.05 and 1.1. It can be noted that the tandem propeller torque also resembles a trend similar to the propeller thrust and is represented by the torque coefficient in Fig.8(b). The open-water efficiency plots represented in Fig.8 (c) indicate that the tandem propeller configuration with a larger aft propeller has higher open-water efficiency; this particular finding can be supported by a previous study [9]

Figure 8 Open water characteristics of the tandem propeller for various diameter ratios. (a) Thrust coefficient. (b) Torque coefficient. (c) Open water efficiency

From Fig. 8(a) and Fig. 8(b), it can be inferred that there is a change in the slope of $K_{T \text{ Total}}$ and $10K_Q \text{ Total}$, corresponding to the diameter ratios 1.05 and 1.10, for a value of advanced coefficient (J) close to 0.6. To understand this phenomenon in detail, the performance of the forward and aft tandem propellers is investigated individually. The $K_{T \text{ Fwd}}$ and $K_{T \text{ Aft}}$ are thrust coefficients of the forward and aft tandem propellers, respectively and are represented in Eq. 5 and Eq. 6. The total tandem propeller thrust coefficient can be expressed in terms of the individual thrust coefficients of the tandem propellers and is represented in Eq.7. In a similar way the torque coefficients can also be expressed.

$$K_{T\ Fwd} = \frac{T_{Fwd}}{\rho n^2 D_{Fwd}^4} \quad (5)$$

$$K_{T\ Aft} = \frac{T_{Aft}}{\rho n^2 D_{Aft}^4} \quad (6)$$

$$K_{T\ Total} = K_{T\ Fwd} + K_{T\ Aft} \quad (7)$$

From Fig. 9(a), it can be observed that the $K_{T\ Fwd}$ for the particular advanced coefficient considered remains almost the same when the diameter ratios are maintained at 0.9, 0.95 and 1.0, i.e., when the forward propeller diameter remains the same ($D_{Fwd} = 0.1$ m, from Table 2). However, when the diameter ratios are varied from 1 to 1.05 and 1.11 (where the D_{Fwd} is larger than D_{Aft}), the $K_{T\ Fwd}$ component increases with a higher magnitude, especially at higher J values. For instance, at $J = 0.2$, the percentage increase in $K_{T\ Fwd}$ is 0.1% and 4%, when the diameter ratio is varied from 1.0 to 1.05 and 1.05 to 1.11, respectively, whereas, at $J = 0.8$, the percentage increase in $K_{T\ Fwd}$ is 5.1% and 8.2% for the same diameter ratio variation. Therefore, this high forward thrust component from the forward propeller at diameter ratios 1.05 and 1.11 can be one of the reasons for the trend of $K_{T\ Total}$ and $10K_{Q\ Total}$ at higher J values close to 0.6 as in Fig. 8(a) and Fig. 8(b).

Figure 9. Thrust coefficient for various tandem propeller diameter ratios at different advance coefficients (a) K_T for the forward tandem propeller, (b) K_T for the aft tandem propeller

For an aft tandem propeller, the diameter remains the same when the diameter ratios considered are 1, 1.05 and 1.1. But unlike the forward propeller behaviour, the thrust produced by the aft propeller reduces drastically. This reduction in $K_{T\ Aft}$ may be due to the influence of induced velocity from the forward propeller. When the diameter ratios of 0.9 and 0.95 are considered, where the aft propeller has a higher diameter than the forward propeller, the thrust contribution of the aft propeller is greater. One possible explanation is that a portion of the aft propeller lies in the region outside the contracted slipstream of the forward propeller, especially the aft propeller tip, and when the aft propeller is of larger diameter than the forward propeller, then a considerable part of the aft propeller will be outside the forward propeller slipstream.

To understand the detailed hydrodynamics, pressure plots at the representative blade section (section at $r/R = 0.7$) are used. Fig. 10 represents the pressure distribution across the non-dimensional blade sections of the forward and aft propellers. C_p represents the pressure coefficient at the particular blade section. The difference in pressure

between the face and back of the propeller is the reason for generating thrust. Therefore, C_p can be considered as an indicator of the propeller thrust. For the convenience of representation, only the diameter ratios 0.9, 1 and 1.10 are used for comparison.

Figure 10. The pressure coefficient of the forward and aft tandem propellers at various diameter ratios. (a) Aft tandem propeller at $J = 0.2$. (b) Aft tandem propeller at $J = 0.8$. (c) Fwd. tandem propeller at $J = 0.2$ (d) Fwd. tandem propeller at $J = 0.8$.

From the pressure plots, it can be inferred that the pressure reversal phenomenon can be observed only at the aft propeller, which can be due to the fact that it is working in the flow field disturbed by the forward propeller. From Fig. 10(a) and Fig. 10(b), it can be concluded that the pressure reversal effect is more prone when the aft propeller diameter is smaller. From Fig. 10(b), it can be inferred that as the loading at the aft propeller decreases, the pressure reversal effect gets minimized, and it can also be observed that the pressure reversal phenomenon occurs mainly when the diameter ratio greater than 1.0, which means the case when the aft propeller has a lower diameter than the forward propeller. From Fig. 10(c), it can be deduced that when the forward propeller diameter is maintained the same, the pressure plot also remains the same even when the aft propeller diameter is varied. Thus, it can be inferred that the aft tandem propeller has a negligible influence on the forward tandem propeller performance. These results are aligned with the findings from a previous study [11]. It can be observed that as the forward propeller size increases, its thrust contribution also increases. Fig. 10(d) represents the forward propeller working at a lower J value. Its observations and inferences are similar to the previous forward propeller findings in Fig. 10(c).

Finally, the primary criterion on which the tandem propeller diameter needs to be finalized must be based on the stern geometry of the vessel considered.

4.3.2 Angular Spacing

As per circulation theory, when the propeller rotates, helical trailing vortices will be shed by the propeller. In the case of tandem propellers, angular spacing between the forward and aft propellers should be selected in such a way that the aft tandem propeller should be positioned away from the helical trailing vortices of the forward propeller. The optimum angular spacing (θ) proposed by a previous study[4], [6]

$$\theta = \frac{L/D}{P_{Fwd}/D} * 360 \pm \left(\frac{180}{Z}\right) \quad (8)$$

The first term $\frac{L/D}{P_{Fwd}/D} * 360$, represents the angular location where the trailing vortices from the forward propeller will be present for a particular axial spacing and forward tandem propeller pitch. This angle is the most crucial one, where positioning an aft propeller must be avoided. In our study, two angular spacings are considered, 38.30 and 83.30 degrees. The first one corresponds to the most optimum angular spacing as per Eq. 8, and the second one corresponds to the most critical angular spacing, which is obtained by considering only on the first term $\frac{L/D}{P_{Fwd}/D} * 360$ of Eq.8

Figure 11. Representation of the angular spacing for the tandem propeller unit. (a) Angular spacing of 38.30 degrees. (b) The tandem propeller model with an angular spacing of 38.30 degrees. (c) Angular spacing of 83.30 degrees.

Fig. 11 (a) and (c) represent the two tandem propeller configurations with angular spacings of 38.30 and 83.30 degrees, respectively, used for the numerical study. Fig. 11 (b) represents the tandem propeller configuration with an angular spacing of 38.30 degrees used for the open water experiments. Fig. 12 represents the $K_{T\ Total}$ at two angular spacings, and it can be concluded that the influence of angular spacing on tandem propeller performance is negligible for the investigated cases.

Figure 12. The thrust coefficient of the tandem propellers at various angular spacings

5 Conclusion

In this present scenario, where there is high traffic in inland water navigation, tandem propellers can be proposed as an economical alternative to conventional propellers due to their operational capability in restricted water depths. The tandem propellers, which are designed using the VLLM procedure, are capable of producing the desired thrust at the required operating conditions and are validated with experimental and CFD results. The aft tandem propellers require a higher mean propeller pitch compared to the forward tandem propellers. When the propeller is designed using the VLLM approach, as the input propeller loading at the design point increases, the mean geometrical pitch difference (which is an output from the design exercise) also increases. This indicates that for higher thrust distribution, tandem propellers need to be designed with a higher pitch distribution. At the same time, with the increase in thrust requirement, the propeller's open water efficiency initially increases and dips down afterwards.

The parametric studies indicate that a tandem propeller unit with a larger aft propeller operates at a higher efficiency and is also capable of producing a higher thrust. It can be noted that when the aft tandem propeller is equipped with a larger diameter, the undesirable pressure reversal phenomenon at the higher propeller loadings can be eliminated. The stern clearance available to fit a propeller is usually more towards the aft, which enables the use of larger aft tandem propellers in practical scenarios. However, the tandem propeller diameters should be considered based on operational requirements and other design constraints such as the stern vessel design. Additionally, the angular spacing between the forward and aft propellers has a marginal influence on the tandem propeller performance. In future, the parametric study has to be extended for other geometrical parameters such as axial spacing, pitch distribution, number of blades, etc., for varying operation conditions.

Acknowledgments

The authors would like to acknowledge the financial support received from the Ministry of Ports, Shipping and Waterways (Sagarmala Cell), Government of India through the Centre for Inland and Coastal Maritime Technology (CICMT) at IIT Kharagpur.

References

- [1] J. S. Carlton, *Marine Propellers and Propulsion*, 2nd ed. Burlington, MA 01803, USA: Butterworth-Heinemann, 2007. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-7506-8150-6.X5000-1>
- [2] J. P. Ghose and R. P. Gokarn, *Basic Ship Propulsion*, 2nd ed. New Delhi: KW Publishers Pvt. Limited, 2015.
- [3] Z. Jialong and X. Huimin, "Open Water Experimental Investigations with Tandem Propellers in Nozzle," 1986.
- [4] S. Qin and G. Yun-de, "Tandem Propellers for High Powered Ships," *Royal Institute of Naval Architects*, pp. 347–362, 1991.
- [5] I. A. Titoff and B. A. Biskup, "Investigation into the Possibilities of Tandem Propeller Application with the Aim of Decreasing the Variable Hydrodynamic Loads Transmitted to a Propeller Shaft," 1966.
- [6] S. Qin, G. Yun-de, and Z. Shu-Zhen, "Theoretical Calculation of Tandem Propellers and their Open Water Test Series," Shanghai Ship and Shipping Research Institute, Ministry of Communications, Shanghai, China, Research Report 78-1–3, 1978.
- [7] B. Djahida and I. Omar, "Impact of Some Geometrical Aspects on the Tandem Co-Rotating Propeller Hydrodynamic Characteristics," *Brodogradnja/Shipbuilding/Open access*, vol. 68, 2017, doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.21278/brod68107>.
- [8] Y. Liu and G. Qingwei, "Numerical investigation on the flow characteristics and hydrodynamic performance of tandem propeller," *Applied Ocean Research*, vol. 101, Aug. 2020, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apor.2020.102292>.
- [9] H. Yao, Y. Liu, H. Zhang, and Q. Zhang, "Numerical investigation on hydrodynamic performance of new canard-configuration tandem propellers," *Applied Ocean Research*, vol. 104, Nov. 2020, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apor.2020.102374>.
- [10] B. Djahida and I. Omar, "Numerical Simulation of the Cavitating Flow Around Marine Co-Rotating Tandem Propellers," *brod*, vol. 70, no. 1, pp. 43–57, Mar. 2019, doi: [10.21278/brod70104](https://doi.org/10.21278/brod70104).
- [11] S. A. Chavan, A. Bhattacharyya, and O. P. Sha, "Open water performance of B-Series marine propellers in tandem configurations," *Ocean Engineering*, vol. 242, Dec. 2021, doi: [10.1016/j.oceaneng.2021.110158](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.oceaneng.2021.110158).
- [12] K. G. Varghese and A. Bhattacharyya, "A Methodology for the Design of Marine Tandem Propellers," *Ocean Engineering*, vol. 321, Jan. 2025, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.oceaneng.2025.120338>.
- [13] K. G. Varghese, A. Bhattacharyya, and O. P. Sha, "Marine Tandem Propellers: Some Design Aspects," in *15th International Symposium on Practical Design of Ships and Other Floating Structures (PRADS 2022)*, Dubrovnik, Croatia, Oct. 2022, pp. 1608–1619.

- [14] A. Bhattacharyya, J. C. Neitzel, S. Steen, M. Abdel-Maksoud, and V. Krasilnikov, "Influence of Flow Transition on Open and Ducted Propeller Characteristics".